

The WHO
**“Systematic Assessment of
Rehabilitation Situation”:**
Development, pilot testing
and utilisation for
cross country comparison studies

Cumulative PhD Thesis
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The WHO “Systematic Assessment of Rehabilitation Situation”: Development, pilot testing and utilisation for cross country comparison studies

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Contents

Acknowledgments.....	4
Executive Summary.....	5
Acronyms	7
Chapter 1.....	8
Introduction	8
1.1 Rationale – Expanding Access to Rehabilitation to Address Population Need	8
1.2 Context – Strengthening Rehabilitation through Informing National Planning.....	10
1.3 Key Concepts – Assessment of Rehabilitation in the Health System.....	13
1.4. Methodological considerations with a focus on stakeholder engagement.....	17
Outline of the thesis.....	19
Chapter 2.....	21
Study 1: Development of the WHO STARS: A Tool for the Systematic Assessment of Rehabilitation Situation.....	21
Chapter 3.....	37
Study 2: WHO Systematic Assessment of Rehabilitation Situation (STARS): Results of the Field Testing in Jordan, Myanmar, Sri Lanka, Solomon Islands, Laos, Haiti, and Guyana	37
Chapter 4.....	52
Study 3: Integrating rehabilitation into health systems: a comparative study of nine middle income countries using WHO's Systematic Assessment of Rehabilitation Situation (STARS).....	52
Chapter 5.....	90
Discussion.....	90
5.1 Summary of main findings	90
5.2 General discussion	91
5.3. Strengths and Limitations	94
Conclusions	95
References	96

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When I started this PhD I had one very clear idea, that it be practical and useful for low- and middle-income countries, I feel that I have achieved this and for that I am deeply grateful.

Executive Summary

Background:

Rehabilitation is an essential health service that aims to optimise the functioning of an individual in the context of their health condition and the environment. The need for rehabilitation is large and growing because of health and demographic trends. While the population's rehabilitation needs increase, in many low- and middle-income countries even the existing needs are largely unmet and hence efforts to strengthen rehabilitation services are needed. A tailored approach to strengthening rehabilitation within a national health system necessitates understanding of the current situation and identification of the priorities to be addressed. 'Health system assessments' (HSA) are regularly performed in countries and used to assess and diagnose the strengths and weaknesses of a health system. Tools that guide HSAs are widely accepted by governments and in 2017 the World Health Organisation (WHO) recognised that guidance for undertaking a comprehensive rehabilitation assessment did not exist and so initiated development of a HSA tool, the "Systematic Assessment of Rehabilitation Situation" (STARS).

Objective:

The objective of this thesis was to develop and pilot test a rehabilitation situation assessment tool and to use it to compare the nature and extent to which rehabilitation is integrated in health systems of low- and middle-income countries. In support of this objective, the following three specific aims were identified: 1). To identify the components on which a rehabilitation situation assessment tool could be based and to draft the tool, 2). To field test the tool with the goal to test its completeness, usefulness, accessibility and feasibility, and 3) To utilize rehabilitation situation assessment reports to describe and compare the status of rehabilitation across low- and middle-income countries.

Methods:

Three related studies were conducted to address the objectives. Study 1 presented the four-phase development process of the WHO STARS and focused on the first three phases of conceptualisation, drafting and consultation with preliminary field testing. Conceptualisation included the identification and content analysis of seventeen HSA tools to inform the components on which the initial draft would be based. Drafting included adapting selected components identified from HSA tools and making them relevant to rehabilitation, it also entailed drafting of the guidance for how to undertake the assessment in a country. A preliminary field test occurred in one country and consultation with diverse stakeholder groups occurred through four consultations, three face-to-face meetings and one online consultation.

Study 2 focused on phase four of the development of STARS, its field testing. Field testing occurred in seven countries with the agreement of their ministries of health. International consultants were trained together in the use of STARS. Through technical and financial collaboration between WHO, ministries of health, international consultants and three international development partners, seven STARS assessments took place over 20 months. The evaluation of the tool occurred through 16 structured interviews and involved interviewees also undertaking a rating exercise of the value of each of the assessment items.

Study 3 focused on objective 3, it described and compared rehabilitation status across middle-income countries using available STARS reports. This was a cross-country comparison study, a type of health system and policy research, it utilised a variable-oriented design. Variables were selected based on their quantifiable (e.g., workforce numbers) or empirical/observable features (e.g.,

rehabilitation policy or plan), and were similarly defined, measured or described across STARS reports. Data was extracted from STARS reports, validated with countries and analysis undertaken.

Results:

Study 1 and 2 showed that it is possible to develop an HSA tool that is targeted to the governments of low- and middle-income countries, designed to support situation assessments of rehabilitation in their countries to inform their national planning. Results of the content analysis informed the drafting of the key elements and assessment items within STARS, as well as the methodology for undertaking STARS, and other features of STARS. Field testing in seven countries found that STARS was complete, usable, feasible and accessible. Outcomes of the later consultations and field testing resulted in small changes to STARS.

Study 3 demonstrated that some information from STARS reports is comparable across countries and that this information can be used in research and contribute to the development of rehabilitation policy and practice recommendations. Nine 'early adopter' countries from the six WHO regions that had implemented WHO STARS were included. Altogether 49 STARS items were selected for the comparison. The nature and extent to which rehabilitation was integrated into health systems was identified and found to be limited with common areas of challenges and difficulty across countries.

Conclusion:

This study developed a health system assessment tool that comprehensively assesses rehabilitation in a health system and when utilised it generates reports that support cross-country comparisons of rehabilitation. STARS, provides a good starting point from which to identify actions that need to be taken at national levels and in so doing contributes to the strengthening of rehabilitation. They can also support the generation of insights into rehabilitation across countries, informing policy and practice recommendations and filling a significant gap in the evidence.

Acronyms

GBD	Global Burden of Disease
GHDP	Global Health Development Partners
HPSR	Health Policy and Systems Research
HSA	Health System Assessment
LMIC	Low- and Middle-Income Country
MOH	Ministry of health
NCD	Non-communicable disease
RMM	Rehabilitation Maturity Model
RTWG	Rehabilitation Technical Working Group
STARS	Systematic Assessment of Rehabilitation Situation
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats
TRIC	Template for Rehabilitation Information Collection
UHC	Universal Health Coverage
WHO	World Health Organization

Chapter 1.

Introduction

This doctoral thesis demonstrates that it is possible to develop a health system assessment tool that comprehensively assesses rehabilitation in a health system and when utilised it generates reports that support cross-country comparisons of rehabilitation.

This first chapter introduces the rationale, context, key concepts, methodology considerations and outline of the thesis that presents three studies.

1.1 Rationale – Expanding Access to Rehabilitation to Address Population Need

Rehabilitation is an essential health service that aims to optimise the functioning of an individual in the context of their health condition and the environment. Difficulties in functioning occur as a result of impairments in body functions (e.g. pain, muscle weakness), limitations in activities (e.g. self-care, walking) and restrictions in participation (e.g. community life, work)(1). Rehabilitation addresses the impact of the health condition with a primary focus on functioning and not the disease. Some challenges exist when attempting to create a definition of rehabilitation that applies for multiple purposes (2–4), however there is wide agreement with the WHO definition of “rehabilitation as a set of interventions designed to optimize functioning and reduce disability in individuals with health conditions in interaction with their environment” (1). Subsequently, rehabilitation services are characterised as those that primarily focus on addressing an individual’s functioning through providing rehabilitation interventions. Rehabilitation is also characterised as a health strategy, one that sits alongside promotion, prevention, treatment and palliative care, a strategy that contributes to overall population functioning (5), and is an essential component for the achievement of Universal Health Coverage(6).

The need for rehabilitation is large and growing because of health and demographic trends. Ageing populations are driving increases in rehabilitation needs with this trend set to continue, between 2015 and 2050 the proportion of the world’s population over 60 years of age will nearly double from 12% to 22% resulting in even larger numbers of people living longer with chronic communicable and non-communicable disease (NCD)(7). Prevalence of common NCDs (e.g., diabetes, hypertension) is increasing and 71% of all deaths are now attributed to NCDs (8), but NCDs also cause significant morbidity and there are growing numbers of people living with their consequences, including with stroke, amputation and vision impairment (9). Injuries also contribute to rehabilitation needs and while globally the overall rate is relatively steady, more people are surviving and living with the long-term consequences of injuries such as low back pain, spinal cord injury and traumatic brain injury(10). Data from the 2019 Global Burden of Disease (GBD) study indicated that 2.4 billion people are living with health conditions that benefit from rehabilitation (2), this is almost one in three of the world’s population. Utilising this data, the leading category of health conditions are musculoskeletal with an estimated 1.6 billion people, then over 600,000 people with vision and hearing conditions, and 300,000 people with neurological conditions. As rehabilitation needs in the population continue to increase, a subsequent expansion of rehabilitation services will be required.

While the population’s rehabilitation needs increase, in many low- and middle-income countries (LMICS) even the existing needs are largely unmet. LMICs commonly have limited rehabilitation services and it is an area of healthcare that is often under-developed and under-prioritised (11).

Studies have demonstrated that rehabilitation services tend to be limited, disparate and commonly unsustainable (12), with services concentrated in tertiary hospitals in major urban areas and low levels available in primary care and rural areas (13–15). Underpinning this are many challenges across multiple components of rehabilitation within the health system, for example leadership and governance may be weak (1), funding limited (12), inadequate workforce supply (16), little information or data available(17)). With many and varied challenges present in LMICs it is important that efforts to strengthen rehabilitation be tailored to each country's needs.

A tailored approach to strengthening rehabilitation within a national health system necessitates understanding of the current situation and identification of the priorities to be addressed. To attain insights into the situation, a comprehensive assessment should be undertaken, one that considers key components of rehabilitation within the context of the health system and explores how these components relate to each other. Therefore, comprehensive guidance for undertaking a health system assessment of rehabilitation will positively contribute to a country's efforts to strengthen rehabilitation.

Health System Assessments (HSA) are regularly performed in countries and used to assess and diagnose the strengths and weaknesses of a health system (18,19). Comprehensive and analytical HSAs lead to improved evaluation of the situation and identification of more targeted recommendations(20). Some HSA methodologies can facilitate higher levels of government engagement and ownership of the assessment findings, and HSAs guided by a standardised tool can produce assessment results that enable comparability across countries and help generate new evidence and knowledge(21). For all these reasons, Global Health Development Partners (GHDP), including the WHO, World Bank, Global Fund, United States Agency for International Development and UNAIDs regularly support HSAs as part of their technical assistance to Ministries of Health (MOH). HSAs commonly occur prior to development of a national health strategic plan or specific health programme plan, and often before health projects are financed.

While working with governments to undertake HSAs, many GHDPs have developed HSA tools (16) to improve the quality of the assessments. These tools can be broadly grouped as 'whole health sector' tools that assess the whole health system, or as 'deep dive tools' that support in-depth study of one specific area of the health system. HSA tools have been developed for many areas of health, for example there is the WHO Assessment Instrument for Mental Health Systems (WHO AIMS)(22) which has been used to support mental health planning(23) and cross country comparisons(24), the WHO Ear and Hearing Care Situation Analysis Tool (EHCSAT) (25) and the WHO Public-private mix for drug-resistant tuberculosis management: a situation assessment tool to engage all relevant care providers in drug-resistant tuberculosis management at country level (26). These tools have been utilised in countries to inform national health planning, additionally, they enable cross-country comparison studies with findings informing global reports and the development of resources targeting LMICs(24). HSA tools are widely accepted and adopted by government and GHDPs and in 2017 the World Health Organisation (WHO) recognised that guidance for undertaking a comprehensive rehabilitation assessment did not exist and so initiated development of a HSA tool, the "Systematic Assessment of Rehabilitation Situation" (STARS).

1.2 Context – Strengthening Rehabilitation through Informing National Planning

In 2017, the World Health Organization (WHO) launched the *Rehabilitation in Health Systems*, a guideline providing system-level recommendations for improving rehabilitation service delivery(1). This guideline conceptualised ‘rehabilitation in the health system’ through consideration of all its relevant components across the whole health system, this meant it reflected rehabilitation services as well as its governance, financing, workforce, information systems, equipment and products etc. This guideline supported a shift in the conceptualisation of rehabilitation that was common amongst GHDPs and LMIC governments from perceiving it as a service targeting people with disabilities (only), towards an essential health service that all the population may need and that should be highly integrated into all healthcare, as well as being available for people with disabilities (11).

In line with the 2017 guidelines, and to respond to the urgent need to strengthen rehabilitation in countries, the World Health Organization (WHO) launched the Rehabilitation 2030 Initiative and a ‘Call for Action’(27) was raised. The ‘Call for Action’ identified ten areas for united and concerted attention to reduce unmet needs for rehabilitation. Among the ten areas identified was to strengthen rehabilitation leadership and planning across healthcare. Planning for rehabilitation, either at national or sub-national levels is crucial for strengthening rehabilitation as it ensures resources are used in the most efficient way to achieve explicit objectives(20). Strategic planning in health is a form of medium to long term planning and aims to “identify, sequence and time medium-term interventions for the health sector, the end product is a strategic plan that guides the activities and the resourcing necessary to achieve the objectives of the plan” (28). In many LMICs, there has been limited rehabilitation planning undertaken by governments(29), development of a rehabilitation strategic plan is recommended to address this situation. A strategic plan is an important step in strengthening rehabilitation as it identifies priorities, vision, objectives and actions that mobilize and direct resources for rehabilitation.

Recognising the value of strategic planning for rehabilitation, the WHO set out to develop a resource to guide this process in countries, this resource is the “Rehabilitation in health systems; Guide for Action”(28). This resource established a four phase, 12 step process to the development and implementation of a rehabilitation strategic plan, figure 1 is from WHO’s resource and illustrates the phases and steps. The first phase is undertaking a situation assessment of rehabilitation so that the MOH has a thorough understanding of rehabilitation in their country, this phase is guided by the STARS tool. The second phase is the process of strategic planning whereby a vision and direction for rehabilitation in the country is identified, it draws on the situation assessment findings, and identifies priorities, objectives and actions needed to strengthen rehabilitation and outlines who, how and sequence they should be achieved. The third phase establishes the monitoring, evaluation, and review process, these ensure that the strategic plan is implemented as intended and achieves its objectives, it allows progress to be tracked and is essential for informed decision-making and accountability. The fourth phase supports the implementation of the plan, guiding operational planning processes. The WHO resource is now available in six languages, English, French, Spanish, Russian, Arabic and Chinese.

Guidance for the first phase and four steps of the process is the STARS tool. STARS ensures that a high-quality, evidence-based and standardized situation assessment and report is completed. The report provides governments with information on the strengths and weaknesses of rehabilitation in the country, priority areas for action, and make recommendations for moving forward. The first step of this process is to prepare for the situation assessment, this ensures the assessment is properly planned and organized. It includes developing a planning document, which is typically a concept

note that includes the objectives, actions, timeline, responsibilities, and budget, ensuring stakeholders know who is doing what. The planning meetings and document also position the government in the leadership role and establishing a national rehabilitation technical working group (RTWG), if it doesn't already exist is one of the governments initial actions. The second step is when key data and information are collected in the country, guided by the Template for Rehabilitation Information Collection (TRIC). TRIC is structured according to the health system building blocks and its information forms a foundation to the situation assessment. The government is responsible for completing one version of this and they often draw upon the RTWG for information. Step three is when the assessment within the country occurs, this may be with a national or international consultant and it entails visiting a variety of rehabilitation services, interviewing key stakeholders, conducting focus groups discussions, and meeting(s) with the RTWG where a SWOT analysis and 'check-in' with exploration and validation of findings utilising the Rehabilitation Maturity Model (RMM) occurs. Finally, in step 4, the report is written and then feedback sought from the government, RTWG and other relevant stakeholders, revisions are made and the report can be finalised and endorsed by government. In this context, the STARS tool was conceptualised, with the primary purpose to guide a comprehensive situation assessment of rehabilitation and to use the findings to inform national, or sub-national rehabilitation strategic planning.

Figure 1. Overview to Four Phase, Twelve Step process within the WHO Rehabilitation in Health System: Guide for Action

Phase 1. STARS

ASSESS THE SITUATION

- Follow the four steps of the **Systematic Assessment of Rehabilitation Situation (STARS)** to undertake a comprehensive situation assessment
- Use the **Template for Rehabilitation Information Collection (TRIC)** within STARS to direct collection of data and information
- Use the **Rehabilitation Maturity Model (RMM)** within STARS to structure the assessment and its findings
- Produce a high-quality situation assessment report

Phase 2. GRASP

DEVELOP A REHABILITATION STRATEGIC PLAN

- Follow the four steps of the **Guidance for Rehabilitation Strategic Planning (GRASP)** to undertake a strategic planning process
- Produce a high-quality strategic plan

Phase 3. FRAME

ESTABLISH MONITORING, EVALUATION, AND REVIEW PROCESSES

- Follow the two steps of the **Framework for Rehabilitation Monitoring and Evaluation (FRAME)** to establish a monitoring framework for the strategic plan and an evaluation and review process
- Use the **Rehabilitation Indicator Menu (RIM)** to guide selection of indicators, then identify baselines and targets

Phase 4. ACTOR

IMPLEMENT THE STRATEGIC PLAN

- Follow the two steps of the **Action on Rehabilitation (ACTOR)** guidance to establish the recurring implementation cycle
- Build capacity of rehabilitation governance and leadership to improve implementation of the rehabilitation strategic plan over time

1.3 Key Concepts – Assessment of Rehabilitation in the Health System

Health System Assessments and their Guidance Tools

Globally, there is widespread use of HSAs, they are regularly performed in countries and broadly used to assess and diagnose the strengths and weaknesses of a health system (12), significant experience and evidence for effective HSAs has developed over time. It is suggested that HSAs tools include; clear objectives; key elements and scope for assessment; and the guidance for how to undertake the assessment (18). When identifying and defining the key elements and scope of assessment items, the following concepts are relevant; 1). health systems components (e.g. health system building blocks), 2). health system goals (e.g. population health outcomes) and 3). health systems functions (e.g. efficient use of resources)(18). During development of STARS, these three components were integrated and characterised under the assessment of the capacity and the performance of the system. Capacity was defined as resources available in the system, such as human, financial, or institutional, that enable action by responsible health system authorities; these are often quantifiable elements that inform status descriptions and enable comparisons across countries. Performance was defined by how well the systems components perform their functions and achieve their goals; for example, provide stewardship and achieve equitable health outcomes(30).

Evidence also suggests that HSAs tools have the following characteristics, that they are participatory and inclusive, analytical, relevant, comprehensive and evidence based (20). Achieving these characteristics requires consideration during the tool development (e.g. ensuring it is evidence based), during identification of assessment items (e.g. making it comprehensive and relevant) and when developing the methods by which the HSA is undertaken in a country (e.g. recommending participatory process with government leadership and convening of a multi-stakeholder rehabilitation technical working group). During this study, an analysis of the content of a variety of HSA tools occurred to help identify all potential opportunities in which desirable characteristics could be incorporated and to ensure these were considered when developing STARS.

Rehabilitation in the Health System

Rehabilitation in the health system is understood through consideration of all of its components within a health system. WHO defines a health system as “all the activities whose primary purpose is to promote, restore or maintain health, and the people, institutions and resources, arranged together in accordance with established policies, to improve the health of the population they serve” (20). Health systems frameworks assist in the conceptualisation of health systems and WHO’s six health system building blocks is one of the most established frameworks (31). This framework and its rehabilitation components were used when identifying the key elements and scope of assessment items during development of STARS. Below are the descriptions of the functions and components of rehabilitation across the six-health system building blocks, these operationalise what is meant by ‘rehabilitation in the health system’ and were utilised during development of STARS:

1. *Governance for rehabilitation:* Rehabilitation governance typically includes identifying priorities and setting the strategic direction for rehabilitation through legislation, policy, regulation, coordination and planning, and then methods for overseeing implementation of actions, establishing accountability and tracking progress.

2. *Financing for rehabilitation:* Health financing focuses on the core functions of: revenue raising (sources of funds, including government budgets, compulsory or voluntary prepaid insurance schemes, direct out-of-pocket payments by users, and external aid); pooling of funds (the accumulation of prepaid funds on behalf of some or all of the population); and purchasing of services (the payment or allocation of resources to health service providers). These functions are achieved through the health and social sector financing schemes that exist in countries, the integration of rehabilitation within all these reflects the financing for rehabilitation in countries.
3. *Rehabilitation information:* Information on rehabilitation can be generated through multiple sources that compose a country's health information systems (HIS). The information serves multiple users and its purpose is to enable decision-makers at all levels of the health system to identify problems and needs, make evidence-based decisions on health policy and allocate scarce resources optimally.
4. *Rehabilitation workforce:* This is composed of a wide range of occupational groups, who deliver care across all levels of the health care. The competencies required to deliver interventions for rehabilitation are generally represented within the professions of audiology, clinical psychology, occupational therapy, prosthetics and orthotics, physiotherapy, and speech and language therapy, as well as by doctors and nurses specialized in rehabilitation medicine. In addition, the rehabilitation workforce often encompasses rehabilitation assistants, technicians, and community-based rehabilitation workers, or other health occupational groups delivering rehabilitation interventions
5. *Essential medicines and technology for rehabilitation:* Assistive technology is the application of organized knowledge and skills related to assistive products. Assistive products maintain and improve individual functioning, they include external devices, equipment, instruments or software that are used to support mobility, vision, hearing, cognition and communication. This includes the system by which they are procured and distributed and made available within the health system. Additionally, under this building block are medicines that are important for rehabilitation such as those that manage spasticity.
6. *Rehabilitation services:* Rehabilitation services are specialized as well as highly integrated form of health care. They are provided at all levels of healthcare, in a highly specialized rehabilitation facility and programme that is for people with complex and intense rehabilitation needs, as well as in other tertiary and secondary care settings. Rehabilitation is crucial in primary care and may include outpatient, outreach and home care in community settings including single or multi professional practices, homes, schools, and workplaces. The 'Rehabilitation in healthcare framework' (28) developed as part of STARS reflects these areas of services (figure 2). Rehabilitation care should be person-centred, evidence-based and outcomes focused. The provision and training in the use of assistive products is an integral component of a rehabilitation service as it aims to improve people's functioning, prevent complications, and promote health.

Figure 2. Rehabilitation in healthcare framework

As mentioned previously, the assessment of both capacity and performance of ‘rehabilitation in the health system’ was prioritised during development of STARS, with assessment of performance requiring consideration of appropriate measures of performance that were feasible within the context of a HSA targeting LMICs. Measurement of the performance of a health system is extensively described, researched and undertaken (32,33), and typically occurs through identification of health system goals and corresponding indicators with clearly defined, valid, reliable and feasible measures (34). Utilising these types of indicators to assess performance is not typical within a HSA, mostly because a HSA is more descriptive and seeks to analyse the situation and understand ‘why’ the sector performs as it does, also, many challenges exist with data availability and quality which would limit feasibility of measurement against specific indicators. For this reason, STARS did not utilise indicators to measure performance but adopted a conceptual framework (logic model) that enabled definition and description of items reflecting both capacity and performance across the systems inputs, outputs, outcomes, impact and the attributes of (high performing) health systems. The logic model reveals the interaction between components through its one-direction sequential structure and provides coherence and structure to assessment items. The assessment items that focus more on performance tend to be located under the outcomes, impact and system attributes. The Rehabilitation Logic Model (figure 3) is included in the WHO Rehabilitation Guide for Action.

Figure 3. Rehabilitation Logic Model

Below are the descriptions of the outcomes, system attributes and impact of rehabilitation, these operationalise and reflect what is meant by 'rehabilitation in the health system' with a focus on its performance, there were utilised during the development of STARS:

1. *Outcomes of rehabilitation – Population coverage of rehabilitation interventions:* This is assessed through consideration of the extent to which people in the population that need rehabilitation have access to it.
2. *Outcomes of rehabilitation – Functioning outcomes:* The outcome of rehabilitation services is assessed through the extent of 'functioning gain' that occurs in people during the period they receive rehabilitation, this is generally measured through functioning outcome measures.
3. *System Attributes – Equity:* Equity is defined as the absence of systematic or potentially remediable differences in access to healthcare across population groups based on common social, economic, demographic or geographic stratifiers.
4. *System attributes – Efficiency:* Efficiency is considered in terms of both allocative and technical efficiency. Allocative efficiency is considered in terms of the overall structure, organization and distribution of rehabilitation services within the health system. Technical efficiency is focused at the level of delivery of rehabilitation services, it refers to how efficiently individual client outcomes are achieved in services.
5. *System attributes – Accountability:* Accountability is the extent to which agencies take responsibility for what they are supposed to do and demonstrate transparency, in relation to rehabilitation.
6. *System Attributes – Sustainability:* Sustainability was defined as the availability of financial (capital) and institutional (human capital) resources in the context of future requirements to deliver rehabilitation, as well as through resilience (ability of rehabilitation to respond, adapt and recover to crisis).
7. *Impact - Better population health and functioning:* This describes functioning at the population level; it takes into account the bodily functions as well as human activities and participation in everyday life. It reflects health and demographic trends, outcomes of health and rehabilitation interventions, and interventions that address the environment.

1.4. Methodological considerations with a focus on stakeholder engagement

This thesis developed a technical product for WHO, hence the concepts and practices regarding the development of technical products (of this nature) were reviewed at the outset. During the review it was found that no single approach existed however there were frequently utilized phases and steps in product development, and these were employed during STARS development. Additionally, as it was a WHO product there was a need to comply with WHO product planning requirements which placed an emphasis on participation and consultation of key WHO stakeholders, in particular WHO Member States.

The key phases in the development of STARS are outlined in Paper 1 (35) and Paper 2 (36), and the methods for cross-country comparison in Paper 3, methodological considerations with a focus on the engagement of stakeholders during the process are highlighted below. As the Papers 1 & 3 discuss much of the methodological consideration, this section focuses on stakeholder engagement during both the product development stage, and its dissemination and utilisation which has occurred since its launch in 2019.

Engagement with WHO during the development and dissemination of STARS.

The conceptualisation and development of STARS was closely supported by WHO, they recognised the benefits of it being a WHO product aimed at WHO Member States from the outset. The author of the thesis had been employed by WHO for five years prior to development of STARS, and remained employed with WHO during development of STARS, working on STARS and other tasks. The product was developed by WHO Headquarters (Geneva, Switzerland), this is the level of WHO that typically develops WHO normative and or technical products.

While WHO Headquarters led development of STARS, engagement with WHO Regional and Country offices was important during the field testing and dissemination of STARS. Field testing required the WHO Regional and Country offices identify governments interested in field testing STARS who also had intention to use the results of STARS to inform their national rehabilitations sector planning. The method for undertaking STARS in countries strongly encourages MOH leadership, necessitating their full engagement so WHO Country and Regional offices had to ensure high levels of MOH commitment to the process. The WHO Regional and Country office personnel were briefed on STARS to identify potential countries, later when countries were selected for field testing the relevant personnel received further training, either through their participation in the face-to-face meeting where the international consultants were trained, or over calls and emails. After its launch in 2019, STARS has been disseminated widely and including the countries where it was field tested there are now 26 countries that have utilised STARS. Engagement of WHO Regional and Country offices has remained integral during the dissemination and utilization period, and WHO Headquarters has conducted multiple phone and video calls, short training webinars and email communication to build their capacity in STARS to ensure the appropriate levels of support was available.

Engagement with other stakeholders during development and dissemination of STARS.

A range of key stakeholders were engaged during STARS development. Their input was sought for three clear purposes; to inform content of STARS; to support field testing; and to support dissemination and utilization in countries, details of this are elaborated below.

Informing the content and drafting of STARS occurred through four consultations, three face-to-face meetings and one online consultation. Key stakeholders included WHO Member States and their respective rehabilitation focal points from within the MOH, these were important as they are key end-users of the product. Representatives from the main rehabilitation professional associations

(e.g., World Physiotherapy Association, World Federation of Occupational Therapy, International Society of Prosthetics and Orthotics, and International Society of Physical Rehabilitation Medicine) were invited to meetings and to nominate representatives to review drafts of the product. Achieving their input and support for STARS was important because their national member organisations play an important role promoting WHO resources and collaborating with the MOH on their implementation. In total, 82 rehabilitation and health experts were consulted, including from seven major rehabilitation professional groups, three rehabilitation service consumer groups and twelve WHO Member States, and an effort was made to ensure stakeholder represented all six of the WHO regions so that regional perspectives were also considered.

To support the field testing of STARS it was essential to work with MOH from LMICs, their 'end-user' perspective on STARS was important for informing the product and contributing to its acceptability and uptake after launch. There was a preliminary field test in Botswana then full field testing in seven other countries, all with very close MOH involvement. Field testing also required engagement with a group of international consultants as through their STARS training and mentoring, they then conducted the STARS assessments. Consultants are also an 'end-user' of the product so their input during field testing was important. Additionally, engagement with selected GHDPs that focus on rehabilitation in LMICs, such as Humanity and Inclusion, World Education and International Committee of the Red Cross, was important. This group contributed through promoting the product directly to the MOH in countries where they work, and on some occasions, they financially supported STARS by paying the costs of the international consultant, their support meant a larger number of countries were included during field testing.

The final purpose for strong engagement with stakeholders during STARS development was to support the dissemination and utilization of the product after it was launched. A very similar group of stakeholders to those already mentioned have been important, i.e., WHO Member States, GHDPs, rehabilitation professional associations and international consultants. Ultimately, this product is designed to be used and benefit governments in LMICs, but it is often through the financial and practical support of GHDPs, including WHO, international professional associations and non-government organisations that makes it possible.

Outline of the thesis

Recognising the need for countries to undertake comprehensive situation assessments of rehabilitation that inform their planning, the objective of this thesis was to develop and pilot test a rehabilitation situation assessment tool and to use it to compare the nature and extent to which rehabilitation is integrated in health systems of low- and middle-income countries

In support of this objective, the following three specific aims were identified:

1. To identify the components on which a rehabilitation situation assessment tool (STARS) could be based and to draft the tool
2. To field test STARS with the goal to test the completeness, usefulness, accessibility and feasibility of the tool.
3. To utilize STARS reports to describe and compare rehabilitation status across LMICs

To achieve the objective and specific aims, three related studies were conducted resulting in three peer reviewed scientific publications (Chapters 2-4).

Study 1. Development of the WHO STARS: A Tool for the Systematic Assessment of Rehabilitation Situation

Study 1 had the objective to present the development process of the WHO STARS which was described as a four-phase process. Study 1 focused on the first three phases of the development process which address Aim 1, the fourth phase addresses Aim 2 and was the focus of Study 2. The development and pilot testing of STARS was undertaken under the auspices of the WHO. It involved four rounds of consultation with rehabilitation and health systems experts, three of which were face to face meetings and one online consultation, all of which were convened and supported by WHO.

The first three phases of STARS development included its 1). conceptualisation, 2). drafting and 3). consultation and preliminary field testing. The conceptualisation phase clarified the objective of STARS, which was to inform rehabilitation planning processes through a comprehensive assessment. This phase also included the identification and content analysis of seventeen HSA tools. Results of the content analysis informed the; key elements and assessment items of STARS; development of a framework based on the logic model and health system building blocks to provide coherence to assessment items and the STARS written report structure; the methodology for undertaking STARS; and other features of HSA tools such as definitions and practical resources, such as sample timelines and budgets.

Drafting required adaptation of the common assessment items from other HSAs to rehabilitation, this included development of definitions of all the STARS assessment items and the method for undertaking STARS in a country. During this phase a framework that utilised the Logic Model and integrated the health system build blocks was developed, this helped to a). reveal the interaction between components through its one-direction sequential structure, for example, the inputs of workforce and financing contribute to the output of accessible services that contributes to the coverage of rehabilitation in the population, and b). support assessment of the performance of rehabilitation in the health system, revealing the outcomes and impact sought. All assessment items were defined and described across a four-level maturity continuum. The study presented the STARS tool, prior to its field testing.

Study 2. WHO Systematic Assessment of Rehabilitation Situation (STARS): Results of the Field Testing in Jordan, Myanmar, Sri Lanka, Solomon Islands, Laos, Haiti, and Guyana

Study 2 had the objective to present the results of the fourth phase of the development process, the STARS field testing, this was carried out in Jordan, Myanmar, Sri Lanka, Solomon Islands, Laos, Haiti, and Guyana and the goal was to test the completeness, usefulness, accessibility and feasibility of the tool. This study addressed Aim 2 of the thesis.

Field testing required agreement and engagement from ministries of health in all countries and the use of international consultants to support the assessment and write the reports. Consultants were trained together in STARS during a workshop June 2018 and field testing occurring over the following twenty months. The evaluation of the tool occurred through structured interviews and involved interviewees also undertaking a rating exercise of the value of each of the assessment items. STARS completeness was evaluated highly, and the usability and feasibility was evaluated moderately high. Evaluation of its accessibility was slightly lower with concerns that components of the STARS tool, particularly the Rehabilitation Maturity Model was complex, the outcomes of the field testing did not result in major changes, and a series of small changes were made to STARS.

Four stakeholder groups closely supported the field testing, these were; 1) ministries of health, who led the process in countries; 2) WHO (all three levels - headquarters, regional offices and country offices) who provided financial and technical support; 3) international non-government organizations - Humanity and Inclusion and World Education who supported the cost of international consultants in three of the seven countries; and 4) international consultants who were trained in STARS and undertook the assessments.

Study 3. Integrating rehabilitation into health systems: a comparative study of nine middle-income countries using WHO's Systematic Assessment of Rehabilitation Situation (STARS)

Study 3 addressed Aim 3, with the objective to describe and compare rehabilitation status, with a focus on identification of the policy implications, across nine middle-income countries using available STARS reports. This was a cross-country comparison study, a type of health system and policy research (HPSR). Cross-country comparisons are an increasingly common form of HPSR, and they can be categorised into case-oriented studies and variable-oriented studies, with the latter being largely driven by the availability of quality data for comparison. This was a variable-oriented study and, as with other cross country comparisons studies, it supported generation of information regarding; 1) national health systems; 2) why they take the forms they do; and 3) lessons for other countries (37).

Nine countries from the six WHO regions that had implemented WHO STARS between August 2019 and February 2021 and had a final government endorsed report agreed to participate, three upper middle-income: Georgia, Guyana and Jordan and the six lower middle-income Nepal, Myanmar, Solomon Islands, Sri Lanka, Tanzania and Zambia. Altogether 49 STARS items were selected for the comparison although limited completeness of some information meant comparisons could only be made by descriptions rather than numerical data.

The findings shed light on common difficulties and challenges for rehabilitation across the health system building blocks and formed a basis for identifying policy and programme actions for strengthening rehabilitation in health systems.

Chapter 2

Study 1: Development of the WHO STARS: A Tool for the Systematic Assessment of Rehabilitation Situation

Chapter 3

Study 2:

WHO Systematic Assessment of Rehabilitation Situation
(STARS): Results of the Field Testing in Jordan, Myanmar,
Sri Lanka, Solomon Islands, Laos, Haiti, and Guyana

Chapter 4

Study 3:

Integrating rehabilitation into health systems: a comparative study of nine middle income countries using WHO's Systematic Assessment of Rehabilitation Situation (STARS)

Chapter 5

Discussion

This thesis was focused on the development of a health system assessment tool that was targeted to the governments of low- and middle-income countries, designed to support situation assessments of rehabilitation to inform their government planning. The thesis demonstrates that it is possible to develop a tool that identifies the key components of rehabilitation within a health system and measures and describes them, it also demonstrates that some information is comparable across countries and that this information can be used in research and make an important contribution to the development of rehabilitation policy and practice recommendations. This final chapter summarises the main findings of the three studies with reference to research aims and also considers the thesis's relevance and contribution to the sector, as well as implications and considerations moving forward, finally it explores limitations.

5.1 Summary of main findings

Specific aim 1 was to identify the components on which a rehabilitation situation assessment tool could be based and to draft the tool, this was addressed in study 1. This included identifying and defining the assessment items that reflected 'rehabilitation in the health system' and the guidance for undertaking the assessment. A logic model was identified to provide coherence and structure to the fifty+ assessment items that were identified. All items were defined and described across a four-level maturity continuum which aids the description and measurement of the situation, additionally a template for information collection identifies and defines key data that supports assessment and be included in the report writing. Detailed guidance for undertaking the assessment was developed utilising a four-step structure.

Specific aim 2 was to field test STARS with the goal to test the completeness, usefulness, accessibility and feasibility of the tool, this was the focus of study 2. The completeness was reported highly by users, the tool was considered comprehensive, particularly for the LMIC settings that it targets. The tool was considered useful in that STARS reports accurately reflected the situation and findings provided a clear basis for recommendations. The tool was accessible in that users rated its structure, definitions, descriptions and practical guidance highly and specific concerns linked to its complexity were addressed in the final draft. Finally, it was found to be feasible and that its 'successful utilisation' is aided through strong engagement of the MOH in the process and support from WHO and often other GHDPs.

Specific aim 3 was to utilize STARS reports to describe and compare rehabilitation status across LMICs, this was the focus of study 3. Cross-country comparisons required identification of items that were similarly defined and measured, extraction and analysis resulted in 49 items that were comparable. While 49 items were identified, not all the countries had available or similarly measured information or data, nonetheless, overall the status of rehabilitation could be identified across countries through the 49 items which characterise the nature and extent in which rehabilitation was integrated into health systems.

5.2 General discussion

5.2.1 *How undertaking STARS contributes to stronger rehabilitation in the health systems of low- and middle-income countries*

Evidence suggests that efforts to improve and expand healthcare are more effective when a health system strengthening approach is taken, STARS defines and operationalises what is meant by ‘rehabilitation in the health system’ and in so doing provides a basis to this approach for rehabilitation. Over recent decades, approaches to strengthening healthcare have repeatedly stressed the importance of ‘health system strengthening’ (30, 36), highlighting limitations to ‘vertical’ programme strengthening approaches (only) and prompting consideration of the multiple and inter-related components of healthcare (39,40)), as well as complexity and competing goals within health systems and risk of being too focused on one element to the detriment of others (41). To some extent, the need to bring a health system strengthening approach to rehabilitation was recognised in the 2017 Rehabilitation2030 Call for Action where relevant aspects of rehabilitation across the health system building blocks are referenced, however STARS built on this through definitions and descriptions, and went beyond building blocks to appreciate performance and define the desirable outcomes (e.g. coverage, equity and sustainability) and attributes of high-performing systems. In this way, it operationalises the multi-dimensional and inter-related aspects of rehabilitation within the health system subsequently supporting the generation of recommendations that account for the ‘bigger picture’ and include multi-pronged and sequenced approaches. Hence, STARS reports are providing a foundation for a more sophisticated response to the multiple challenges faced in countries, which is in line with health system strengthening approaches to improving healthcare.

A range of rehabilitation services are necessary to meet population needs, STARS makes clear the core types of services required, this is broadening the understandings of policy and programme decision makers and informing the vision for future service development in countries. Rehabilitation services in LMICS tend to be under-developed with some levels of care, such as specialised rehabilitation services for people with complex needs and rehabilitation within primary care being very limited (42–44), misconceptions about rehabilitation and a limited appreciation for what services should be available within healthcare are common in LMICs (45). Subsequently, building comprehensive and accurate understandings about rehabilitation services is an important foundation, leading to more effective efforts to expand and strengthen them. STARS facilitates these understandings through its definitions of the fifty components for assessment, it elucidates what an optimal rehabilitation system looks like by describing the mature version of each component. Of the 50 components, 27 focus on rehabilitation services and this builds stakeholder understandings of what makes up a comprehensive range of rehabilitation services in a country. An expanded vision for rehabilitation services in LMICs is evident in anecdotal reports after undertaking STARS, whereby policy and programme decision makers describe new insights into how to structure, organise and incrementally increase rehabilitation services. It is also being reflected within the national rehabilitation strategic plans through inclusion of frameworks that outline the future organisation of the country’s rehabilitation services (46,47) and investment into service expansion where these gaps have long existed (48).

STARS reports are generating evidence informed, location specific and tailored recommendations about how to strengthen rehabilitation, and report recommendations are being integrated into both rehabilitation strategic plans as well as other health plans in countries. The structure of a STARS report is designed to produce recommendations that are justifiable based on report findings. It does this by assessing and describing the situation, based on data and information from the country, across the health system building blocks and across the outcomes (i.e., access, coverage, equity and sustainability), utilising the assessment items and definitions within the Rehabilitation Maturity Model. At the end of the STARS report, there is a summary of the sector's strengths, ensuring that the progress that has been made to improve rehabilitation is clearly recognised. Then there is a list the priority areas requiring attention, these take into account the gaps between what exists in the country and a mature rehabilitation system (defined in Rehabilitation Maturity Model), these are justified with reference to earlier reported findings. After this, STARS reports include a list of recommendations that correspond to the priority areas for action and reflect specific details of the local situation while drawing on good practice approaches with reference to other available WHO technical products where appropriate. This overall report structure is what supports generation of justifiable, location specific and tailored recommendations to be used to inform planning. Strategic planning for rehabilitation has been historically weak with few plans in place (29), and similarly the inclusion of rehabilitation within other health plans (e.g. national health strategic plans, NCD plans, mental health plans) has been limited (1). Recommendations made in STARS reports are clearly forming a basis to strategic planning evidenced by the corresponding alignment of objectives within rehabilitation plans. More importantly, these actions are now taking place resulting in early signs that rehabilitation services are getting stronger in countries that have undertaken this process.

Leadership is crucial for driving positive changes to policy and practice, the process of undertaking STARS is strengthening national rehabilitation leadership and creating improved sectoral coordination. Rehabilitation, as a field of practice, is often quite fragmented because there are different professionals (e.g. rehabilitation doctor, physiotherapist, speech language therapist, prosthetist and orthotist) who work on different aspects of healthcare, for example they are not focused on one disease, body organ, stage of life or even phase of care (49), but on all and often simultaneously. In this way, rehabilitation services are often fragmented, more so than other areas of health care, and this has meant less opportunities for rehabilitation stakeholders to collaborate which subsequently leads to less sectoral coordination and joint leadership. Limited rehabilitation sector leadership has been a concern of WHO's for some time (50) and this informed the decision that STARS guidance include MOH leading the process and creating a RTWG. The RTWGS have played an important role and often become an ongoing mechanism for multi-stakeholder coordination in countries. An evaluation undertaken by a GHDP about experiences found leadership and coordination had strengthened during the process of undertaking STARS (51), additionally STARS recommendations had drawn attention to this challenge resulting in creation of a rehabilitation focal unit in the MOH to support sector leadership.

5.2.2. How generating information about the status of rehabilitation across multiple countries enables research and informs development of further technical support and products

STARS reports contribute to Health Policy and Systems Research (HPSR) by enabling country case studies and comparative studies across countries, both of which build knowledge on the situation including the common and varied challenges experienced within LMICs. The ability to undertake studies across countries is especially important for rehabilitation as there is a sparsity in HPSR which has limited the insights into the status across countries (52). Cross-country comparison studies can

start to fill the knowledge gaps, both through generating hypothesis that inform further studies, and through identifying the common strengths and challenges which inform the policy and practice recommendations that are generalizable across countries. STARS is being utilised in 26 countries, with more country assessments planned in coming years, soon these STARS reports will provide an even greater insight into the situation. In time, as HPSR capacity increases for rehabilitation, a multi-research partner consortium could be developed, and STARS reports could contribute to further studies.

Greater information about rehabilitation in LMICs is important for the identification of priority areas for further technical support and the development of technical products. With limited resources available to support the strengthening of rehabilitation in LMICs, it is important that what is available is used most effectively, targeting areas/topics that are most in need of resources and most likely to generate positive change in countries. In this context, GHDPs are investing in the development of programmes and products and the findings from STARS reports can inform selection and design of these. Internally within WHO, the analysis of STARS reports has already led to a greater understanding of the extent to which rehabilitation is limited within primary care and the need to make this a higher priority for advocacy, technical support and development of WHO products. For example, the cross-comparison study revealed rehabilitation in primary care to be most limited level and WHO is developing further guidance for primary care and seizing the opportunity of greater political focus on this level to advocate for inclusion of rehabilitation. Finally, undertaking STARS and the cross-country comparison paper has shed light on the information and data that is available in countries and in this way can inform WHO on the development of a feasible set of global indicators for rehabilitation that can be used to monitor global progress.

5.2.4. Implications and moving forward for the STARS tool

In time, STARS will require revisions and updates, these will be needed to reflect learnings from its utilisation, changes in rehabilitation sector priorities and evidence, and to ensure ongoing alignment with other WHO products. An example of changes in priorities is the recent prioritisation of telerehabilitation. The shift to telemedicine during the COVID pandemic is well documented (53,54), however the initial version of STARS did not explicitly address this mechanisms for service delivery because of its under-developed status in many LMICS, but a revised version of STARS will need to address this. Remaining aligned with new WHO products is another reason for updates, for example, WHO will soon launch the Package of Interventions for Rehabilitation (55) and this product can be used to develop standards for what services should be available at each level of healthcare, better reflection of these could occur in an updated STARS tool. Developing updated versions of tools, such as a HSA tool is a common practice for WHO products. The WHO Rehabilitation Program is planning an evaluation and review of STARS so that a new version can be launched approx. 5 years after its initial launch which will be in 2024, this length of time is appropriate given WHO resources and the need to allow for high levels of experience and learning from the product.

5.3. Strengths and Limitations

Strengths:

One of the key strengths of this thesis was that it developed a novel tool that clearly met a need and is now being regularly utilised. The tool's development included consultation and review by many stakeholders, including the future consumers of it, and through this process a degree of acceptance was achieved that has contributed to moderately high levels of utilization given it was launched only eight months before the global COVID-19 pandemic began. Support from WHO during its development and it being a WHO product is also a strength as there is a greater acceptance and trust in WHO products by MOH in LMICs. The thesis included a cross-country comparison study of 9 countries, one of the first studies of this size of countries that included many comparable variables for rehabilitation.

Limitations:

There are several limitations that should be noted in regard to this thesis, these are grouped across three areas; the methodology employed during development of STARS; limitations to STARS as a health system assessment tool; and limitations to its effective utilisation in countries.

Limitations in the development of STARS were discussed in papers 1 and 2. Key limitations of study 1 include not being systematic and exhaustive in the identification and analysis of all HSA tools however the 17 identified were deemed sufficient for development of STARS. During study 2, the seven countries identified for field testing represent a convenience sample in that the governments who agreed to undertake STARS were already cooperating with a GHDP on rehabilitation. During study 3 the key limitation to the cross-country comparison study was that while the 49 items identified were comparable not all the countries had the data or information available or similarly defined to enable the comparisons, however, enough countries did to support the study and make the results meaningful.

Limitations to STARS as a health system assessment tool include the extent to which it assesses all components of rehabilitation in health systems. STARS focus on LMICs resulted in decisions to reduce the number of components assessed so that it was less complex to use and more aligned with the rehabilitation typically available in LMICs. This meant that STARS has less applicability in high income countries where there is typically a more complex and expanded set of rehabilitation services. Unfortunately, this has meant that no high-income country has undertaken STARS and therefore could not be included in the current or potentially future cross-country comparisons studies based on STARS reports. Another implication of this decision is that even in LMICs there are occasions when countries have a particular type of rehabilitation service and specific guidance for this is lacking within STARS. An example of this that has arisen is vocational rehabilitation services, as well as the telerehabilitation that was mentioned previously. It should however be noted that while STARS may not have guidance for the assessment of all types of rehabilitation, it does not limit describing these services by report writers (typically international consultants) and they are encouraged to do so.

Limitations to its effective utilisation in countries are mostly due to the limited reliable data and information that is available in some countries. Accurate assessments of the situation rely on information and data, and where countries cannot source this the accuracy of assessment is impacted. The occasion where this is most concerning is when a country cannot produce reliable information about its workforce numbers and available rehabilitation services. Information on the workforce and services are crucial for informing conclusions regarding access, quality, coverage and

equity. This has somewhat occurred in countries where there is a highly privatised healthcare system and unregulated workforce, with weak data collection by government across government and private sectors. On these occasions, the RTWG has been asked to make and agree on an estimate which allows the report writer to make cautious conclusions. An unforeseen challenge to its effective utilisation occurred during the pandemic when there was an inability for international consultants to visit countries. Fortunately, it was possible to adapt the methodology and it was remedied by the identification of local consultants who with additional remote training and technical support were able to undertake the assessments. While this methodology was referred to in the current version of STARS, its higher levels of use and success suggests it could be elaborated further in an updated version of STARS in future.

Conclusions

Our study has developed a HSA tool that comprehensively assesses rehabilitation in a health system and when utilised it generates reports that support cross-country comparisons of rehabilitation. STARS contributes to the strengthening of rehabilitation by laying a strong foundation for improved leadership, coordination and planning of rehabilitation in countries. The process necessitates government leadership of a multi-stakeholder group and through assessing the status of rehabilitation it makes recommendations that inform a range of planning efforts. Multiple STARS reports are now enabling the generation of insights into rehabilitation across countries, informing policy and practice recommendations and filling a significant gap in the evidence. Each of these are extremely important if we are to realise the vision of WHO's Rehabilitation2030 Initiative and the Sustainable Development Goal 3, "ensuring healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages".

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